

Figure 3: HLA-E induction on tumor cells limits RIG-I induced NK cell cytotoxicity.

(a-d) Primary NK and NK-92 cytotoxicity measured on WT cells and three HLA-E^{-/-} A-431, SK-OV-3, EFO-21, and Caco-2 cell lines at E:T ratio = 0.6:1. The target cells were previously stimulated with 0.4 μ g/ml RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or control RNA (3p-ssRNA) as indicated in Fig. 1a. Shown are individual values and mean \pm SD from 4 (SK-OV-3 and Caco-2) and 6 donors (A-431 and EFO-21), or pooled data from at least 4 independent experiments with the NK-92 cells (b). The observed contribution to NK-cytotoxicity (c, d) was calculated as average for: HLA-E deletion (HLA-E^{-/-} - WT), RIG-I stimulation (WT 3p-dsRNA - WT 3p-ssRNA), and the potential, synergistic effect of combination ((HLA-E^{-/-} 3p-dsRNA - WT) - (HLA-E^{-/-} - WT) - (WT 3p-dsRNA - WT 3p-ssRNA)) normalized to 100% of the total cytotoxicity observed for the combination. (e, f) Twenty-hour NK cytotoxicity assay on A-431, SK-OV-3, and A549 WT and HLA-E^{-/-} cell lines previously stimulated with 1000 U/ml IFN γ for 24h or control medium at E:T ratio 5:1 and 2.5:1 measured with primary NK cells (e, shown are the means of at least 4 individual donors and SD) or NK-92 (f, pooled data from at least 3 independent experiments). (g) Primary NK cytotoxicity on tumor cells transduced with lentiviral particles expressing HLA-E alleles (Lentivirus #1), or IRES and GFP sequences (Lentivirus #1), or a lentivirus control expressing only GFP (EV). Statistical comparisons were performed using two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Šídák's (a, b, e, f) or Dunnett's (g) post-hoc test. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.